

Palacký University
Olomouc

 UCLouvain

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The EU in the volatile Indo-Pacific region

EUVIP

Overview of Guest Lectures Organized by the EUVIP Project

1. 1. 2023 – 31. 12. 2025

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Overview of the project

Project title	The EU in the volatile Indo-Pacific region
Project acronym	EUVIP
Project number	101079069
DOI	10.3030/101079069
Funding	HORIZON EUROPE Framework Programme
Program	HORIZON.4.1 - Widening participation and spreading excellence HORIZON.4.1.2 - Twinning
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03
Website	www.euvip-project.com
Coordinator	Palacký University Olomouc (UP), ROR: 04qxnmv42 University of Helsinki (UH), ROR: 040af2s02
Partners	UCLouvain (UCL), ROR: 02495e989 University of Copenhagen, ROR: 035b05819 (until 2023-08-31) Lund University, ROR: 012a77v79 (from 2023-11-01)
Start date	2023-01-01
End date	2025-12-31
Project summary	<p>Through its concise training, research, communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities EUVIP will significantly contribute to shaping the new, rapidly developing academic field of Indo-Pacific Studies. The project will raise the awareness of the stakeholders (academia, civil society, politics, and broad public) of the strategic, political, and economic significance of the volatile Indo-Pacific region for Europe and for a values-based European approach towards this region. Together with its seven dissemination partners, the EUVIP consortium will create a sustainable European Indo-Pacific experts network and knowledge hub with strong dissemination channels to national and EU policymakers in order to strongly contribute to the EU's Indo-Pacific strategy and policies. In addition, EUVIP will establish a Myanmar Centre at Palacky University in Olomouc (Czech Republic) to connect academia with politics and the civil society. EUVIP will build on UP's strong expertise on Southeast Asia and China's Belt and Road Initiative, supplemented by the</p>

complementary expertise of three leading European research partners (University of Helsinki, University of Copenhagen, and Université Catholique de Louvain). To further improve UP's excellence capacity and resources, the three expert partners will provide training to UP's early career researchers, PhD students, and research management administrators. This transfer of knowledge will result in a much higher international visibility of UP academics through an increased number of publications in world-class journals, an increased number of Horizon 2020 project applications, an increased reputation and attractiveness of UP for renowned international scholars and students, and increased mobility and employability of the UP staff.

Overview of the guest lectures

Guest lecture goal

Transfer of knowledge – Strengthening of Indo-Pacific and EU competences and research skills of senior researchers, early career researchers, and PhD students

List of Guest Lectures

(Selection of Publicly Announced Events)

[Guest lecture 1](#): India's Past and Present: The Evolution of its Political and Economic Systems and Current Challenges

[Guest lecture 2](#): The EU's New Assertive Advocacy of Norms and Values in its Relations with the Indo-Pacific

[Guest lecture 3](#): Cambodia's Political Model

[Guest lecture 4](#): Publishing for Early Career Researchers

[Guest lecture 5](#): Op-ed writing

[Guest lecture 6](#): Where is Southeast Asia in the Indo-Pacific?

[Guest lecture 7](#): The Relations between Latin America and the Caribbean and the Indo-Pacific Region

Related to

Project objective 1, Work package 2 (Task 2.2)

Guest lecture 1

India's Past and Present: The Evolution of its Political and Economic Systems and Current Challenges

Heribert Dieter

German Institute for International and Security Affairs & University of Potsdam

16. 10. 2023

Zoom

Guest lecture summary:

The lecture examined the evolution of India's political-economic systems within the broader geopolitical context of the Indo-Pacific region and it addressed current major challenges in India's economic and political trajectory.

Related materials:

- [Guest lecture webpage](#)
- [Guest lecture recording](#)

The EU's New Assertive Advocacy of Norms and Values in its Relations with the Indo-Pacific

Jörn Dosch

University of Rostock

18. 3. 2024

Palacký University Olomouc

Guest lecture summary:

The lecture examined the European Union's increasingly assertive advocacy of norms and values in its relations with the Indo-Pacific.

Related materials:

- [Guest lecture webpage](#)

Cambodia's Political Model

David Hutt

Central European Institute of Asian Studies (CEIAS) & The Diplomat

4. 11. 2024

Palacký University Olomouc

Guest lecture summary:

The lecture examined Cambodia's political system in the context of the Hun family's rule since 1985—first under Hun Sen and, since 2023, under his eldest son, Hun Manet. It addressed the key question of how to characterise Cambodia's contemporary governance structure, discussing whether it can be understood as a feudal system, an autocratic regime, or a failed democracy.

Related materials:

- [Guest lecture webpage](#)

Publishing for Early Career Researchers

Julie Yu-Wen Chen

University of Helsinki

11. 11. 2024

Palacký University Olomouc

Guest lecture summary:

The lecture addressed key aspects of academic publishing relevant to early-career researchers. It focused on common questions and challenges encountered in the publication process, drawing on practical experience within academia. The presentation covered strategies for publishing academic journal articles and books, as well as guidance on transforming a doctoral thesis into a monograph.

Related materials:

- [Guest lecture webpage](#)

Op-ed writing

David Hutt

Central European Institute of Asian Studies (CEIAS) & The Diplomat

11. 11. 2024

Palacký University Olomouc

Guest lecture summary:

The lecture focused on the principles and practical aspects of op-ed writing. It examined how to craft clear, engaging, and powerful opinion pieces suitable for newspapers and magazines. Particular attention was given to working with editors, refining and editing texts, responding to criticism, and effectively approaching relevant media outlets for publication.

Related materials:

- [Guest lecture webpage](#)

Where is Southeast Asia in the Indo-Pacific?

Felix Heiduk

German Institute for International and Security Affairs

11. 4. 2025

University of Helsinki

Guest lecture summary:

The lecture examined Southeast Asia's position within the evolving geopolitical framework of the Indo-Pacific. It analyzed the region's strategic location at the intersection of the Indian and Pacific Oceans and its significance both great and middle powers, who seek to engage with the region due to its central role in global trade and security. The discussion addressed the apparent paradox between Southeast Asia's geostrategic importance and its historically peripheral role in Indo-Pacific debates, and assessed the region's influence in the context of ongoing Sino-US rivalry.

Related materials:

- [Guest lecture webpage](#) (EUVIP website)
- [Guest lecture webpage](#) (University of Helsinki website)

Guest lecture 7

The Relations between Latin America and the Caribbean and the Indo-Pacific Region

Ana Soliz de Stange

Helmut-Schmidt-University/University of the Armed Forces in Hamburg

13. 10. 2025

University of Helsinki

Guest lecture summary:

The lecture examined political and trade relations between Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) and the Indo-Pacific region. It highlighted that, although existing scholarship often focuses on LAC–China relations, countries in the region engage more broadly with Indo-Pacific actors both bilaterally and multilaterally, including through expanding trade with South Korea, India, and Japan, and participation in forums such as APEC.

The presentation analyzed the impact of shifting diplomatic recognition from Taiwan to the People’s Republic of China since 2017 and assessed how these developments shape Indo-Pacific dynamics. It addressed the strategic importance of LAC countries for the Indo-Pacific region, as well as the opportunities and challenges they face. The lecture included case studies of key bilateral relationships between LAC countries and the People’s Republic of China, India, and Taiwan, focusing on commercial and political-strategic dimensions.

Related materials:

- [Guest lecture webpage](#) (EUVIP website)
- [Guest lecture webpage](#) (University of Helsinki website)
- [Guest lecture recording](#)